

Beyond One Million Genomes

1+MG Recommendations for a Data Access Governance Framework (Research Purposes)

v 28 February 2022

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Summary of Recommendations

The 1+MG's goal of effective and responsible cross-border access to and secondary use of genomic and related-health data for research purposes requires the 1+MG to adopt a common and coordinated data access governance framework. Governance includes *institutional* policies (e.g., rules, criteria, conditions), processes, and agreements. In the data access domain, governance determines who may have access to data, for what purposes, and under what conditions. The 1+MG mandate as outlined in the Declaration is to establish a federated network of national or regional Data Holders. Data Holders are the institutions based within countries with the authority to grant or refuse access to certain genomic and health-related data.¹ Data Holders typically establish a Data Access Committee (DAC) to review access requests. The basic rationale of these recommendations is to preserve access authority and accountability within countries (especially as it relates to protection of the fundamental rights and interests of data subjects), while at the same time streamlining researcher access to a large-scale virtual European research cohort. The central elements of the recommended 1+MG data access governance framework are detailed here.

No common access/use conditions (but a common process to communicate access/use conditions)

- The 1+MG cannot establish one common set of data access and use conditions, as valuable data may come from many different countries and contexts, subject to diverse data access and use conditions.
- To ensure the predictable and efficient administration of the data access process, data must be accompanied by standard administrative (rights) metadata², which transparently describes the conditions of data access and use (e.g., permitted areas of

¹ Data Holder “means a legal person, public body, international organisation, or a natural person who is not a data subject with respect to the specific data in question, which, in accordance with applicable Union or national law, has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal data or non-personal data.” “See a proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European data governance ([Data Governance Act](#)) (Analysis of the final compromise text in view to agreement v 10 Dec 2021) Art 2(5).

² Rights metadata is “administrative metadata defining the ownership and the legally permitted use of a resource.” (European Open Science Cloud, [Glossary](#) 2020).

Beyond One Million Genomes

B1MG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951724

research). These metadata should respect a common, structured vocabulary endorsed by the 1+MG.

Data access decisions made within countries

- Data Holders will be based within countries at the national, regional, or local level. There will be no central, European institution with authority to grant access to data.
- 1+MG Member States are encouraged to centralise authority over data access decisions to the extent legally, politically, and practically feasible, in order to simplify the organisational complexity of the 1+MG network and to pool limited national resources and expertise needed to properly govern access to data (e.g., by establishing genome initiatives or permit authorities at the national or regional level).
- Data Holders have discretion to determine how those decisions are made, but are encouraged to establish a data access committee (DAC), following best practices for reviewing and approving data access requests.
- The 1+MG Access Office should be able to flag and mediate decisions inconsistent with rights metadata. Currently no formal redress mechanism is envisaged for inconsistent access decisions. Mechanisms may be introduced in the future under European and national data governance legislation.

A coordinated data access process

The access request and decision-making process will include the following elements:

- A common dataset catalogue and record-level query system. These will allow researchers to identify scientifically relevant datasets or individual records (according to variable-level inclusion criteria). *See more below.*
- A common portal for launching data access requests.
- A common data access request form template, including all relevant criteria any Data Holder across Europe needs to make an access decision.
- A common 1+MG Access Office to efficiently:
 - o review administrative aspects of data access applications (e.g., identity and eligibility checks),
 - o coordinate the communication of access requests and decisions,
 - o record and publish information about access decisions.
- National coordinating node to coordinate the timely communication of access requests and decisions to Data Holders within countries.
- A common (or at least a standard) Data Use Agreement to streamline contracting.
- A common website for reporting on what projects have been approved to access 1+MG data.

Integrated data search and access request workflow to ensure data minimisation

- The 1+MG infrastructure must integrate the record-level search workflow with the access request workflow to enable requesters to find relevant datasets, subgroups, or record types according to variable-level inclusion criteria, and then select the resulting data to include in their access request.
- All Data Holders must therefore adopt a standard query system that allows their data to be query data at the variable level, as a minimum FAIRness standard, and also to enable granular operation of the GDPR data minimization principle.

- To ensure data minimization, data requesters must identify variable-level inclusion criteria as part of their access request, justified by their data analysis plan.
- The 1+MG Access Office will conduct a basic eligibility check to confirm the datasets and/or record types requested match the variable-level inclusion criteria in the data analysis plan. Data Holders (or more specifically their DACs) are free to further scrutinise the scientific justification of the variable-level inclusion criteria.
- As variable-level search involves processing of personal data to generate statistics, the 1+MG infrastructure for federated search requires a robust data protection and security framework to avoid disclosure of personal data as well as inappropriate processing (e.g., user authentication, output controls (e.g., $n > 5$), query budgeting, monitoring, terms of use).

Areas for future exploration by 1+MG

1+MG should continue to explore the following possibilities:

- a standard vocabulary of data access and use conditions for tagging data with administrative rights metadata.
- an access negotiation process that allows data requestors and Data Holders to communicate about data availability and project feasibility in advance of data access requests.
- an optional, central data access committee, perhaps made up of national representatives.
- models of mutual recognition between Research Ethics Committees (RECs), founded on common minimum standards for REC review. If each project requires multiple REC reviews, this could lead to duplicative oversight processes and access delays, without increasing protection of individuals.

2. Background

2.1. 1+MG

The aim of 1+MG as described in the [Declaration](#) is to coordinate secure, distributed and authorised cross-border access to a cohort of 1+ million genomes and related health data for research, healthcare, policy-making purposes. Access is to be provided in a federated (not centralised) network. The Declaration calls for the development of a “coordinated data governance framework” necessary to facilitate Europe-wide large-scale processing. This data governance model will define “the terms and conditions for distributed access to genomic data across borders” and use of the data.

As agreed by the Signatory Countries in the [Scope of the 1+MG initiative](#), the 1+MG can support data access to qualified researchers within 1+MG Member Countries, and may also be extended to researchers across the broader EEA and even globally with appropriate safeguards in place.

2.2. Scope of this document

Beyond One Million Genomes

B1MG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 951724

This document proposes recommendations for a 1+MG common and coordinated data access governance framework for research purposes. Data access for healthcare and policy-making purposes will be addressed separately and subsequently.

Data access governance concerns institutional policies and processes that aim to balance two overarching aims: to make data effectively, transparently and fairly available to qualified users for appropriate research purposes, while also ensuring respect for the fundamental rights and interests of sequenced individuals and those of other stakeholders (e.g., Data Holders).

Data access governance is typically described in the context of a particular data collection or database (containing multiple data collections) overseen by a single institution. Data access governance in research contexts typically includes the following elements:

- an access policy defining the conditions of access and use.
- an access request form (covering criteria for making access conditions).
- review by a data access committee (DAC). DACs are typically interdisciplinary committees with appropriate expertise to review and approve access requests.
- a Data Use Agreement defining e.g, purpose limitation (for a specific project), security (e.g., only in a secure environment), as well as conditions on IP, publication, commercialization, and archiving.
- record keeping, reporting, and/or publishing on data access decisions.

1+MG will be a federated network of numerous Data Holders, each of which will have its own data access governance. Like with data or technical interoperability, a lack of alignment across governance policies and processes can frustrate the integration and re-use of data across networks of institutions. The opportunity for 1+MG is to establish a *framework* that outlines *common* and/or *coordinated* data access governance across this network. In addition to the elements above, a data governance framework for a network of institutions must also clarify which institutions have the authority to grant or refuse access to data.

In a federated system, it is essential to distinguish between coordination at the institutional layer (governance) and the technical layer (infrastructure). Access governance involves institutional rights, obligations, policies, and processes, which are largely independent of the technical layer of 1+MG (e.g., the certified data hubs where data are curated and managed, and the secure processing environments in which data are processed). Secure and interoperable data and technical infrastructure are necessary but not sufficient to enable meaningful data access, integration and re-use across a network. These networks also need to be sufficiently aligned at the institutional level, through common and coordinated governance processes.

The following sections review the main recommendations.

3. No common access and use conditions (but common process to communicate access and use conditions)

3.1. No Common Access and Use Conditions

An access policy is simply a policy stating data access and use conditions, including the purposes for which data may be used (e.g., certain types of research projects), criteria for who may access data (e.g., access limited to certain sectors or geographies), how long access may be granted, etc.

Genomic and related health data included in 1+MG will come with different access and use conditions, given that the data may come from different countries, sectors (e.g., research, healthcare, industry), and contexts (including different consent choices made by individuals).

The 1+MG will not impose a common access policy on data included in 1+MG, as this would potentially mean excluding many valuable datasets that may be subject to more restrictive conditions.

The downside of having no common access policy is fragmentation. Different data collections (or even subgroups or individual record sets) will be subject to different access and use conditions. This raises challenges for researchers seeking access, as it may not be easy for them to determine if certain data are available to them. The resulting lack of predictability may discourage data access requests. It also raises administrative challenges for reviewing data access requests, as the criteria may differ depending on the data collections requested.

3.2. Common Requirement to Tag Data with Standard Rights Metadata

Metadata is descriptive information or statistics describing a resource, such as a data collection or even an individual record, that makes it possible to find, understand, and meaningfully re-use data. ([EOSC Glossary](#)) Rights metadata is a type of administrative metadata that essentially describes data access and use conditions. Rights metadata can also apply to a resource, such as a database, data collection, or individual record (e.g., individual consent choices).

While 1+MG gives Data Holders flexibility to determine what conditions apply to data, it must require that all included data be tagged with standard, structured rights metadata. This requirement is essentially about transparency towards the research community: the conditions of data access and use - whatever they are - must be transparently stated. This transparency allows researchers to determine what data are legally and ethically available to them for their intended purpose. This transparency is also essential for the administration of the access request process, which must confirm the data are in fact legally and ethically available.

However, even transparency is not sufficient in the context of a network of institutions, each with its own databases containing diverse data collections, subject to diverse access and use conditions. Here it is also important that rights metadata - like other types of metadata - are not only transparent but also standardised. If every institution uses different terminology to describe access and use conditions, this increases the interpretation burden and unpredictability for researchers. Where researchers seek to integrate multiple data collections, this interpretation burden may quickly become impracticable. Standard rights metadata follows a controlled vocabulary of agreed upon terms, reducing interpretive uncertainty.

It would then be presumably straightforward to represent standard rights metadata in a machine-readable structure. This would lead to additional benefits, such as allowing researchers to search for data across a network that are not only scientifically relevant, but are also ethically and legally available to them. Moreover, data access requests could be similarly tagged with rights metadata, allowing for automated eligibility checks against the rights metadata of the requested data, streamlining the access process for all parties involved. (Note we are not suggesting that this metadata be used for automating access decisions).

One challenge to fulfilling this recommendation is the lack of a standard administrative rights metadata vocabulary fit for the purposes of 1+MG. One existing standard is the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health [Data Use Ontology](#). This primarily focuses on general ethics conditions derived from consent form, and may need to be extended to cover European data protection conditions and possibly also other legal conditions such as IP. A further challenge is that all the 1+MG Member Countries would need to agree on the standard vocabulary that would describe access and use conditions of both future collections as well as already-collected data. Finally, ongoing investment in resources and expertise will be needed to support Data Holders to label their data. We recommend 1+MG continues to explore opportunities and barriers to developing, approving, and implementing a standard rights metadata vocabulary. In the longer run, we recommend the European Commission invests in the development of a fit-for-purpose standard.

4. Authority to make access decisions stays within countries

The Declaration declares that 1+MG is a “federated network”, and calls for a governance model addressing “the terms and conditions for distributed access to genomic data across borders” and use of the data. The 1+MG will be federated at the level of infrastructure, with data physically residing in 1+MG certified repositories within countries. It is also clear from this mandate that the ultimate authority to grant or refuse access to data will stay within the 1+MG Member Countries. In other words, there will not be a central European database, data access committee, and/or permit authority. Authority to grant or refuse access is distributed across the countries. Moreover, the Data Holders (institutions with the authority to grant or refuse access) may be further distributed within certain countries to regions or even local institutions. The rationale for this approach is the assumption that most countries will insist on maintaining control over this sensitive (and valuable) data. This may also already be built into national legislation that is difficult to change. And finally this approach centres trust and accountability within countries.

Because the authority to grant access is distributed across and potentially also within countries, this raises an immediate coordination challenge. A single data access request to the 1+MG may implicate numerous decision-makers, raising challenges for efficiency, timeliness, and consistency of access decisions. The access process is potentially inefficient, because multiple Data Holders each need their own data access committees and processes to review a single access request. There is a serious risk of losing the users over the delay when waiting on multiple decisions. And issues can also arise of inconsistent decisions across decision-makers (even where their access criteria are similar and transparent), which may be an indication of non-compliance with applicable requirements or discrimination towards requesters.

To address this problem, each country should seek to centralise (within the country) authority to grant or refuse access, to the degree that is legally and practically feasible. Where possible, a single Data Holder should be established per country or per region. A fully distributed network of potentially hundreds of Data Holders would be highly inefficient (requiring access governance resources at each institution), and would likely lead to massive delays. There are different ways to centralise access authority within a country or region: setting up a single, large-scale national or regional genomics initiative; setting up a national or regional Data Holder who is a (sole or joint) controller for making data available for research purposes (this Data Holder can be an intermediary who receives data from a network of initial research/healthcare organisations)³; or setting up a national or regional permit authority legislatively authorised to grant access to data held by a network of Data Holders (more suitable for networks of public sector controllers - an advantage here is the local controllers can maintain authority over their data for other purposes). This centralised Data Holder can be equipped with the mandate, necessary resources and expertise to responsibly and efficiently review access requests, and offer timely and consistent decisions. This recommendation requires only a best effort on behalf of 1+MG Member Countries, as effective centralization of Data Holder may require changes or introduction of legislation, and may encounter resistance from institutions who do not want to give up control over their data. This recommendation aligns with the future direction of the *Data Governance Act*.

Regardless, where there are multiple authorities within a country, there must be a national coordinating node to administrate and communicate access requests and decisions in a timely manner.

4.1. Best Practices for Data Access Request Reviews

While authority to grant or refuse access remains within countries, the 1+MG can develop best practices to guide these authorities on how to make data access decisions. For example, the GA4GH [Data Access Committee Committee Guiding Principles and Procedural Standards Policy](#) guides organisations responsible for data access decisions including defining the aims of access review; establishing transparent application processes; establishing Data Access Committees (e.g. purpose, scope and structure, roles, responsibilities), and defining Standard Operating Procedures to ensure decisions are made in a timely, efficient, responsible and consistent manner. Regardless, access decisions should be made in a certain time frame, with limited and justified extensions.

4.2. Redress

Currently it is unclear what kinds of redress mechanisms are possible where a Data Holder refuses to grant access to a cross-border researcher without acceptable justification, or where a Data Holder is non-responsive. Under current conditions, Data Holders within countries

³ In one scenario, data are simply transferred to the intermediary, who is then sole controller for storage and making data available. A possible modifier is a joint controllership arrangement, where the data collecting organisation delegates responsibility for access decisions to the intermediary. The data collecting organisation could potentially retain a veto over the access decision (thus maintaining ultimate authority) but that would need to be exercised in a certain time period (thus enabling timely decisions).

retain ultimate authority over access decisions. We do not recommend that this governance framework require any of this authority to be subject to a European appeals body. 1+MG must at a minimum permit researchers to submit objections to access decisions to the 1+MG Access Office, which will be passed on to the Data Holders. Data Holders are encouraged to have their own internal appeal processes as part of best practice access governance. However, we do recommend that inconsistencies becoming apparent between communicated access and use conditions and access decisions be flagged and mediated by the 1+MG Access Office (see below) before the decision reaches the requester. We recommend that all Data Holders must agree to allow the 1+MG Access Office to publish data about response times, and possibly also about common reasons for not granting access, to transparently inform requesters. The 1+MG should plan ahead to align with future European and national legislation that is likely to provide for formal redress procedures in certain contexts, upon which 1+MG could rely.⁴

5. A Coordinated Data Access Process

With decision-making authority fragmented across institutions within countries, the proper functioning of 1+MG as a virtual European research cohort necessitates every effort to streamline the data access process. We recommend that 1+MG must establish a number of common administrative forms, services, and processes. Otherwise researchers will not only be confronted with a plethora of access and use conditions, but also different access processes, especially where aiming to integrate data from several countries or Data Holders. Separate and independent procedures are likely to slow or in some cases even practically prevent European scale studies. Recommendations to address these problems include:

5.1. A Common Dataset Catalogue

A common dataset catalogue is already envisaged for 1+MG. The catalogue should include standard rights metadata that transparently describes dataset access and use conditions, allowing researchers to filter their data search accordingly.

5.2. A Common Record-level Query System

We recommend that Data Holders be required to adopt systems to enable searching for relevant records at the variable-level, to facilitate FAIRness as well as compliance with the data minimisation principle of the GDPR.

5.3. A Common Portal to launch data access requests

⁴ The *Data Governance Act* for example provides conditions to grant access must be non-discriminatory, proportionate and objectively justified with regard to categories of data and purposes of the envisaged use and the nature of the data. A right of redress at least for public sector access, that “shall be laid down in national law and shall include the possibility of review by an impartial review body with the appropriate expertise, such as the national competition authority, the relevant access to documents authority, the supervisory authority established in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 or a national judicial authority, whose decisions are binding upon the public sector body concerned.”

A single web-portal for launching a data access request across Europe, without researchers needing to understand the complex institutional and technical arrangements of who decides on access and where data physically resides.

5.4. A Common Data Access Request Form Template

1+MG establishes a single application form template for research, so that the access request workflow is independent of the data source(s). The content of this template will be based on access criteria considered by Data Holders (which tend to be similar across existing resources - see Appendix A). This will require all Data Holders to standardise the format of the core criteria they require to make access decisions. Having a common template does not require all Data Holders to consider exactly the same access criteria. The template can include additional criteria that may be needed by only certain Data Holders. The requester will only be prompted to fill out these additional aspects where specific datasets are requested.

The requester will need to define and justify the relevant datasets and/or records requested, as well as the initial access period request (e.g., 1-5 years) rather than being a standard access condition. Data Holders have the final say if the duration is justified. The access period should in principle be specific to the project but may be paused during periods of inactivity for data minimization purposes.⁵

5.5. A Common 1+MG Access Office

We recommend the 1+MG establishes a common 1+MG Access Office to streamline common, administrative aspects of access requests, and to ensure the timely communication of data access requests (to national coordinating nodes) and decisions (to researchers requesting access). This central service would not disrupt the ultimate authority of the Data Holders to grant or refuse access, but could significantly reduce their collective workload. It is not efficient if the same basic administrative assessment is made independently several times. This suggestion provides an economy of scale. Even if countries re-check the assessment, the main points are already worked out and the national decision makers do not have to start from scratch.

This common 1+MG Access Office would have the following functions as part of the administrative review of access requests:

- Verification of requester's identity.
- Verification of completeness and eligibility of access request.
- Consistency check between the different elements of the access request: e.g., project description, lay summary, data analysis plan, data requested are justified by analysis plan, research ethics application and approval for research project (by a competent ethics board or REC), and administrative metadata tags describing the project.
- Consistency check of access request administrative metadata with the administrative metadata of selected datasets and their availability conditions.

⁵ Rules for data access after the approval will be part of the Data Use Policy.

- A common website for reporting and publication of information about approved projects, number of requests, response times of national nodes and/or Data Holders.

The 1+MG Access Office may reject applications for formal reasons (incompleteness of request; wrong documents/information), and send it back to the requester for remedy. A complete application will be passed on to the relevant national coordinating nodes for decision. The 1+MG Access Office will then collate decisions and integrate feedback (justifications were applicable) from national coordinating nodes and communicate to the requester. Some feedback to the decision makers may be needed where there are decisions based on conflicting justifications to try and resolve any misunderstandings or different interpretations. For reasons of fairness and consistency, requesters should not be provided with conflicting statements about why their access request was rejected. The ultimate decision is however made within countries, so there may in some cases be differences of opinion that must be respected and justified towards the data user.

Where access is approved and the common Data Use Agreement is signed, the 1+MG will issue technical data access credentials.

5.6. A Common Data Use Agreement

A common, non-negotiable Data Use Agreement must be employed by all Data Holders and data users. One contract will cover each data access grant, independent of the source of the data, or the number of separate data collections. Where a consortium requests access, each partner institution will have to sign an agreement. To avoid misuse, this contract should be complemented with user training (e.g., webinar and test). Agreeing on a standard agreement will depend on establishing a common 1+MG policy concerning data protection elements (e.g., roles), security standards for secure computing environments (including periodic expiry/renewal of access credentials), intellectual property, commercialization, publication, and archiving.⁶ A list of typical clauses is found in Appendix B.

Where appropriate, signature delegations to the 1+MG Access Office should be seen to speed up the administrative process, though all Data Holders will be party to the contract. This is justified by economies of scale. The 1+MG Access Office is only allowed to sign following a positive access decision by the Data Holder; therefore, the risk of delegation should be minimal; in line with the concept of a virtual cohort.

6. Integrated Search and Access Workflow

The 1+MG infrastructure must integrate the federated search workflow with the access request workflow to enable requesters to find relevant datasets, subgroups, or record types according to variable-level inclusion criteria, and then select the resulting data to include in their access request. All Data Holders must therefore adopt a standard query system that allows to query data at the variable level, as a minimum FAIRness standard, and also to enable granular operation of the GDPR data minimization principle. To ensure data

⁶ initial considerations will be developed in a Data Use Policy by WP2, and will be complemented by the work of WP7 (Industry) on intellectual property.

minimization, data requesters must identify variable-level inclusion criteria as part of their access request, justified by their data analysis plan. The 1+MG Access Office will conduct a basic eligibility check to confirm the datasets and/or record types requested match the variable-level inclusion criteria in the data analysis plan. Institutions within countries with the authority to grant or refuse access (or more specifically their DACs) are free to further scrutinize the scientific justification of the variable-level inclusion criteria. As variable-level search involves processing of personal data to generate statistics, the 1+MG infrastructure for federated search requires a robust and standardized data protection and security framework to avoid disclosure of personal data as well as inappropriate processing (e.g., user authentication, output controls (e.g., $n>5$), query budgeting, monitoring, terms of use).

7. Research Ethics Committee (REC) Approval

Research uses of personal data accessed through 1+MG generally require REC review and approval. This oversight needs to be coordinated across 1+MG. Data requesters will generally need to seek a local REC review and approval of the specific research project. It is problematic if each Data Holder insists on an additional research ethics review of specific data access requests, as this would lead to duplicative review and delay, without necessarily increasing data subject protection. They may also be questions of accountability and jurisdiction limiting the ability of a Data Holder's REC to review a project from an external institution or country.

The 1+MG should further explore opportunities for mutual recognition between RECs. National legislation in some countries may require a local REC review on the Data Holder side. Data Holders would also need to trust the requester's REC in order to forgo a local review of the project. A mutual recognition model will therefore depend on minimum standards for REC review across 1+MG Member Countries. 1+MG may need to rely on broader standardisation initiatives to do this across the EU/EEA, or even internationally. Alternatively, 1+MG could permit Data Holders to conduct their own research ethics review as long as this did not require information beyond the common data access request form template, and could be conducted within the agreed upon timelines, and at the Data Holder's own costs.

1+MG could explore offering a central ethics review service in certain circumstances, e.g., where data are requested by a researcher from a third country outside 1+MG members; where a data user does not have a local REC; or where there are concerns about the competence of the data user's local REC. In addition, 1+MG may want to set up a central ethics committee with representatives of different countries in cases where there may be an overall concern with an application, such as novel AI approaches. Where the project affects vulnerable groups, advisory committees of representatives may be involved as part of national/local data access committee decisions (this is subject to the discretion of the authority granting access). 1+MG could offer vulnerable group representative consultation services organised at the European level, with representatives from different countries.

Ethics and data protection risks across 1+MG could be continuously monitored by a standing 1+MG ethics committee (either the continuation of WG2, or a new committee made up of national representatives).

Appendix A. Common Data Access Request Form Elements / Access Criteria

- Project title
- Name and contact details of the Principal investigator of the project
- Information about the institution
(Institution needs to be registered including information on signing official and DPO; where several signing officials are applicable, the relevant official is to be chosen)
- Persons who will have access to the data (PI and his/her group)
- Scientific abstract
- Lay summary of project
- Data analysis plan that describes the data types and analysis approaches to be employed to achieve the goal of the project
- Estimated project duration
- Funding source
- Research ethics application and decision for the specific project
- Machine readable characterisation of project based on controlled vocabulary (e.g. field of research, commercial versus pre-competitive research, data types to accessed, etc.), (checked for consistency with analysis plan and other project documents by 1+MG Access Office).
Justification: this will be necessary for using automated tools to check that access requests are consistent with data availability conditions
- Selected data or types of data to be accessed (should be automatically selected from the catalogue browsing and/or Beacon search)
- Needs to be confirmed by a signing official at the requester's institution or requester needs to be "white-listed" at his/her own institution.
- In case of consortia with other researchers requiring access: the same form needs to be filled in (ideally the software / portal allows "invitation" of collaborators who can build on the information already provided by the person launching the access request.
- Information on required processing environment (required to assess the feasibility of conducting the research in the 1+MG environment, the risk of processing, compile processing agreement and provide a quote on compute costs where applicable)
- Once data access is granted, an additional contract will be needed to access the computing infrastructure, including the estimated costs of processing:
 - Specification of accessed data types to be migrated from 1+MG to computing environment.
 - Information if additional own data will be uploaded including specification of data types and amount (required for compiling a contract including processing agreement and assess storage / ingestion cost where applicable)

Appendix B. Common elements of a Data Use Agreement

- Identification of legal capacities
- Context
- Definitions
- Purpose / object of the agreement
- Obligations of data users
- obligation to process in the 1+MG secure environment [to be extended where needed]
- Obligation of 1+MG entities (including processing agreement)
- Intellectual property
- Financial provisions
- Term and termination
- Breach of agreement
- Consequences of breach of the duties
- Liability
- Applicable law- Jurisdiction
- Arbitration
- Exhibits
 - o Identity of participating parties to the processing and description of their activities (e.g. involved data centres)
 - o Project description including data analysis plan
 - o 1+MG data security framework

